

MORAL RENEWAL AND CULTURAL DEVELOPMENT OF UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract: This article talks about the role of national cultural centers in Uzbekistan in interethnic harmony. The author, relying on scientific data, studied and analyzed the specific aspects of the role of national cultural centers in Uzbekistan in interethnic harmony based on available literature.

Key words: Uzbekistan, national cultural centers, interethnic harmony.

1. Introduction.

In the implementation of a large-scale program of spiritual and moral renewal and cultural development of Uzbekistan, an objective study of national history plays a significant role, in particular the characteristics of the spiritual and cultural life of the people at different stages of its history. For the culture of the people is a dynamically developing process, the content and specificity of which are determined by the historical conditions of its era[1].

National cultural centers serve to meet the national cultural needs of representatives of different nationalities and peoples living in Uzbekistan, to preserve customs, traditions and values and to pass them on to the next generation. The existing cultural centers of the Republic of Uzbekistan have been operating legally based on the current legal and regulatory documents and their own charter. The uniqueness of national-cultural centers is that they are interested in learning, preserving and developing national culture, language, customs, values, traditions and rituals characteristic of a particular nation. National cultural centers voluntarily unite citizens of Uzbekistan.

The first national-cultural centers in our country were established by Koreans, Kazakhs, Jews, and Armenians in 1989 [4]. The real development and prosperity of these centers began after our country gained its independence. During the years of independence, a wide opportunity was created for their effective activity. If in 1992 there were 10 national-cultural centers, in 1995 their number reached 72, and by 2003 there were 135. Today, the committee of international relations and friendly relations with foreign countries cooperates with 150 national cultural centers, 38 friendship societies and 38 societies of compatriots abroad operating in our country [5]. They consist of republican cultural centers, regional, city and district cultural centers.

2. Material and Methods.

Ensuring the active participation of representatives of different nationalities living in the Republic of Uzbekistan in socio-political, spiritual-educational and cultural processes is one of the important directions of the activity of national-cultural centers. Also, the centers carry out friendly cooperation of nationalities with compatriots in foreign countries, establishment of cultural and educational relations and their development. The main tasks of the Republican International Cultural Center are to help strengthen the solidarity and inter-ethnic harmony among the citizens of our country. National cultural centers in our country carry out the following types of activities: a) music and theater studios, training in the study of the native language, history, writing, literature, folklore, theater and painting arts, national traditions and crafts, national sports and games. organizes groups and Sunday schools in accordance with

current legislation; b) national culture, national language; seminars, conferences, roundtables, festivals and meetings to study and promote national art forms and national traditions; c) organizes choirs and art groups.

The purpose of establishing national cultural centers in the Republic of Uzbekistan is to study the preservation and development of national culture, language, traditions, and to establish national cultural centers on the territory of the republic in order to protect the customs and traditions of each nation living in the Republic and their interests. This was due to insufficient attention being paid to the field of inter-ethnic relations in the former Soviet era. During this period, the idea of a single state and a single people was put forward by the former Soviet government. During the time of the former Union, national politics in Uzbekistan was one-sided, and the issue of national culture was not resolved in any of the Union republics. There was always a one-sided approach to the national issue by the former Center. Although the ideas about culture were explained in the Constitution of the former USSR, they were not proven in practice. That is why restoration, development and preservation of national culture rose to the level of state policy after we gained independence.

3. Results.

At the same time, a special concept on raising the spiritual and educational level of our people, strengthening the material and technical base of culture and art institutions, and supporting industry representatives was approved in our country.

Nowadays, all peoples of Central Asian countries pay great attention to preserving their cultural heritage. Today, 158 organizations of our compatriots are operating in 20 countries, such as the USA, Great Britain, Germany, Israel, the Baltic States, Azerbaijan, Russia, Tajikistan, Kazakhstan, and Kyrgyzstan. By actively using the mechanism of "people's diplomacy", they make a significant contribution to maintaining a peaceful and prosperous life, developing friendly relations and cultural-educational ties with foreign countries, and establishing close and mutually beneficial relations with compatriots abroad.

Currently, studies are conducted in 7 languages in educational institutions of our country. TV and radio shows and broadcasts are broadcast in 12 languages, newspapers and magazines are published in more than ten languages. Representatives of different nationalities living here say "Uzbekistan is our common home!" united under the slogan, celebrate wedding ceremonies and various holidays together. The most important thing is that necessary conditions have been created to preserve the national traditions of all brothers and sisters. Today, national cultural centers play an important role in public diplomacy, that is, strengthening mutual trust and good neighborliness between countries, expanding cultural and humanitarian relations with neighboring countries. People's lives, worldviews and lifestyles are rapidly changing under the influence of globalisation.

Examples of culture are not created mechanically by the mass of the people, but by the most advanced people, intellectuals and scientists working in various spheres of social life. Also, the main majority part of society adopts advanced examples of culture, which ensures harmony between nations. Interethnic harmony and religious tolerance are among the main principles of a democratic society. Tolerance ensures harmony among citizens and prevents the emergence of social conflicts.

4. Discussion.

Today, not only in our country, but also in the world, religious tolerance, mutual respect and mutual understanding among religious denominations are becoming vital principles. In this regard, due to the results of the fair policy carried out from the first days of independence, as well as the high quality of our people, today representatives of all nationalities and religions live peacefully and harmoniously in our country. As the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev noted: "In the years of independence, a new stage in the development of inter-ethnic relations began in our country. Development of the culture of tolerance and humanity, strengthening of inter-national and inter-civilian solidarity and harmony, education of the young generation in the spirit of love and loyalty to the Motherland on this basis was defined as one of the most important priorities of the state policy in Uzbekistan. All this found its full expression in life."

The peoples of the Central Asian region had a positive impact on the development of world science and culture in the Middle Ages, and in the new century, they are striving to make significant use of the world's cultural achievements. Implementation of fundamental reforms in our socio-political life in the years of independence, as the first President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Islam Karimov noted, "depends on the formation of creative intellectuals who widely promote the cultural achievements of the peoples of advanced countries" [2].

Democratic society develops on the basis of cooperation and interaction between different nations and peoples, social groups and classes. Natural and geographical conditions, climate, methods of labor organization play an important role in the emergence of different cultures among peoples. Overemphasis on individuality and originality in national culture can ultimately lead to national limitation, disconnection from world civilization, and as a result conflict between different nations. The diversity of property relations creates a unique difference in the culture of different social groups and classes.

It is not for nothing that urban and rural culture, intelligentsia and popular culture differ from each other. Such a difference is connected with the methods of labor organization, the existence of different ownership relations, and both the artificial strengthening of these differences and their immediate disappearance cause negative consequences for the society. Social mobility (mobility or flexibility of social classes and groups) is a law that objectively applies in the conditions of market relations. As much as this professional ethics is important in the improvement of production relations, knowing and understanding the uniqueness of the culture of different classes and social groups is also important in the integration of different layers in the society. As Emile Durkheim noted, "the social division of labor creates a solid foundation for further strengthening of solidarity among members of society. The emergence of new professions and specialists further strengthens the connection between social groups and strata" [3].

5. Conclusion.

In recent years, the political-legal, socio-economic image of our society has changed rapidly, and it is felt that new relationships, new opportunities and values are forming in our lives. Especially "human rights and freedoms", "rule of law", "openness", "freedom of speech", "freedom of religion and belief", "public control", "gender equality", "inviolability of private property", "freedom of economic activity", fundamental democratic concepts and life skills such as "harmony" are now becoming a reality.

Only the state power built on the basis of such principles is truly a people-oriented, democratic power. The political-legal, socio-economic and spiritual-educational roots of the state and society with national harmony will be strong and strong. Supporting the activities of cultural centers, creating conditions and opportunities is of great social and political importance.

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